

Supplementary Information: Exit Wavefunction Reconstruction from Single Transmission Electron Micrographs with Deep Learning

Jeffrey M. Ede, Jonathan J. P. Peters, Jeremy Sloan, and Richard Beanland

{j.m.ede, j.peters.1, j.sloan, r.beanland}@warwick.ac.uk

S1. ADDITIONAL EXAMPLES

Example applications of ANNs are shown in figs. S1-S18, and source code for every ANN is available in [1]. Phases in $[-\pi, \pi)$ rad are depicted on a linear greyscale from black to white. Wavefunctions are cyclically periodic functions of phase so distances between black and white pixels are small.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. M. Ede, "One shot exit wavefunction reconstruction." online: <https://github.com/Jeffrey-Ede/one-shot>, 2019.

Fig. S1: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 multiple material training set wavefunctions for unseen flips, rotations and translations, and $n = 1$ simulation physics.

Fig. S2: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 multiple material validation set wavefunctions for seen materials, unseen simulation hyperparameters, and $n = 1$ simulation physics.

Fig. S3: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 multiple material validation set wavefunctions for unseen materials, unseen simulation hyperparameters, and $n = 1$ simulation physics.

Fig. S4: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 multiple material training set wavefunctions for unseen flips, rotations and translations, and $n = 3$ simulation physics.

Fig. S5: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 multiple material validation set wavefunctions for seen materials, unseen simulation hyperparameters, and $n = 3$ simulation physics.

Fig. S6: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 multiple material validation set wavefunctions for unseen materials, unseen simulation hyperparameters are unseen, and $n = 3$ simulation physics.

Fig. S7: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 validation set wavefunctions for restricted simulation hyperparameters, and $n = 3$ simulation physics.

Fig. S8: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 validation set wavefunctions for restricted simulation hyperparameters, and $n = 3$ simulation physics.

Fig. S9: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 $\text{In}_{1.7}\text{K}_2\text{Se}_8\text{Sn}_{2.28}$ training set wavefunctions for unseen flips, rotations and translations, and $n = 1$ simulation physics.

Fig. S10: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 $\text{In}_{1.7}\text{K}_2\text{Se}_8\text{Sn}_{2.28}$ validation set wavefunctions for unseen simulation hyperparameters, and $n = 1$ simulation physics.

Fig. S11: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 validation set wavefunctions for unseen simulation hyperparameters and materials, and $n = 1$ simulation physics. The generator was trained with $\text{In}_{1.7}\text{K}_2\text{Se}_8\text{Sn}_{2.28}$ wavefunctions.

Fig. S12: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 $\text{In}_{1.7}\text{K}_2\text{Se}_8\text{Sn}_{2.28}$ training set wavefunctions for unseen flips, rotations and translations, and $n = 1$ simulation physics.

Fig. S13: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 $\text{In}_{1.7}\text{K}_2\text{Se}_8\text{Sn}_{2.28}$ validation set wavefunctions for unseen simulation hyperparameters, and $n = 3$ simulation physics.

Fig. S14: Input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 224×224 validation set wavefunctions for unseen simulation hyperparameters and materials, and $n = 3$ simulation physics. The generator was trained with $\text{In}_{1.7}\text{K}_2\text{Se}_8\text{Sn}_{2.28}$ wavefunctions.

Fig. S15: GAN input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 144×144 $\text{In}_{1.7}\text{K}_2\text{Se}_8\text{Sn}_{2.28}$ validation set wavefunctions for unseen flips, rotations and translations, and $n = 1$ simulation physics.

Fig. S16: GAN input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 144×144 $\text{In}_{1.7}\text{K}_2\text{Se}_8\text{Sn}_{2.28}$ validation set wavefunctions for unseen simulation hyperparameters, and $n = 1$ simulation physics.

Fig. S17: GAN input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 144×144 $\text{In}_{1.7}\text{K}_2\text{Se}_8\text{Sn}_{2.28}$ validation set wavefunctions for unseen flips, rotations and translations, and $n = 3$ simulation physics.

Fig. S18: GAN input amplitudes, target phases and output phases of 144×144 $\text{In}_{1.7}\text{K}_2\text{Se}_8\text{Sn}_{2.28}$ validation set wavefunctions for unseen simulation hyperparameters, and $n = 3$ simulation physics.